

Supplementary Material for FedLoRASwitch: Efficient Federated Learning via LoRA Expert Hotswapping and Routing

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A Pre-prompts Used in FedLoRASwitch

The following pre-prompts were used to guide the base model and the specialized LoRA experts:

1. **Base Model:** You are a helpful assistant.
2. **Indian-history Expert:** You are a historian.
3. **General Expert:** You are a helpful assistant.
4. **Math Expert:** You are a math expert. Solve systematically.
5. **Code Expert:** You are a world-class AI coding expert and engineer with deep experience in Python, Ruby, SQL, Java, JavaScript, C#, Go, Rust, and other modern programming languages. You always write clean, efficient, and scalable code following the latest industry standards. When the user asks a question:
 - a) Carefully read the question and identify the language, framework, and version requested.
 - b) Provide a concrete, runnable code example with comments explaining each step.
 - c) Briefly explain why this is the best solution (e.g., design patterns, performance, security).
 - d) When relevant, link to official documentation or other authoritative resources.

Your tone is educational, professional, and helpful. Always tailor your answer to the user's skill level and context.

B Win-Lose-Tie (WLT) Evaluation Questions

The following questions were used for the Win-Lose-Tie (WLT) qualitative evaluations comparing the base model against FedLoRASwitch with its specialized experts.

B.1 WLT Coding Questions

1. "You are given a matrix of m rows and n columns. Write a function that calculates the transpose of the given matrix. `matrix = [[1, 2, 3], [4, 5, 6], [7, 8, 9]]`"
2. "Create a list comprehension that takes all the elements of `list_one` and creates a new list where all the elements are doubled. `list_one = [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]`"
3. "Construct a SQL query to find all columns in a table called "customers" where the first name is equal to "John". Additionally, modify the query to only select the third column of each result and exclude any rows where the age is greater than 30."
4. "Write a Java program to find the largest element in a given array."
5. "Create an HTML form with radio buttons for selecting gender."
6. "Write a Ruby program to search for a specific item in an array of strings. `array = ["Apple", "Banana", "Mango", "Orange"]`"

B.2 WLT Indian-history Questions

1. "What marked the period of the Gupta dynasty in terms of progress?"
2. "What facilitated the growth of trade in the Sangam economy?"
3. "What were some important towns and craft centers during the Sangam period?"
4. "What were the characteristics of Vedic literature, and what texts are considered as Vedic?"
5. "What are the four separate collections included in the Mantra category, and what is their significance?"
6. "Describe the role of artisans and merchants in town administration during the Gupta period."